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EFFECT OF DYSPROSIUM OXIDE ON POLYANILINE

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ABSTRACT

The in-situ polymerization technique was employed to synthesize pure polyaniline (PANI) and PANI-Dy₂O₃ composites at room temperature. Physical characterization was performed on the PANI and composite are SEM-scanning electron microscopy, FTIR-Fourier transform infrared spectra and XRD-X-ray diffraction. Whereas thermal equilibrium by TGA, DSC, and AC conductivity of these composites were investigated. The interactions between PANI and Dy₂O₃ were demonstrated by the outcomes of SEM, IR and XRD. The weight percentage of Dy₂O₃ has an effect on the conductivity of PANI. Rare earth oxide PANI's interaction plays a significant role in the thermal stability as shown by TGA and DSC analysis.

KEYWORDS: *polyaniline, dysprosium oxide, AC conductivity.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

A family of compounds composed of monomeric units is represented by polymers with conjugated chemical bonds only if specific situation is met, such as doping, which ensures the polymer's electronic conductivity. To create materials that can be used in various applications. Metals and semiconductors can be replaced by treating them as conductivity, low density, and readily treatable (1). Electrochemical capacitors have been

subject to considerable attention over the past few years on the basis of higher power energetic. When compared to conventional dielectric capacitors, this capacitor greater density and long cycle performance (2). Three types of materials were primarily used in capacitor application studies. ruthenium dioxide, carbon and conducting polymers. An intriguing class of conducting polymer are utilized as electrochemical capacitors because of their exceptional properties. The conducting polymer possesses a high capacitive energy density while being low in material cost (3). Despite their advantages, conducting polymer have a shorter cycle life. The insufficient stability of redox sites in the polymer backbone causes ion transport to be slow during the widely cycled redox interaction (4). Polyaniline (PANI), a delegate from a conductive polymer family, discriminates itself by a simple synthesis and high-level environmental surveys (5). Using the chemical oxidation method, PANI/Dy₂O₃ composite were produced and their dielectric properties were analysed. Research has focused on electrical transport in polymeric materials as an area of interest in research because solid state devices have great potential with these materials (6). These materials are particularly significant because they bridge the gap between conducting polymers and nanoparticles (7).

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION:

2.1. Chemicals:

Aniline, Ammonium Dichromat, Hydrochloric Acid, and doping element as Dysprosium Oxide all chemicals were taken S.D. Throughout the synthesis of PANI-Dy₂O₃ composites, fine chemicals and distilled water were used.

2.2. Synthesis of Pure PANI:

An in-situ chemical polymerization reaction method was employed in the synthesizing of PANI. The formation of aniline hydroxide can be achieved by adding Monomer aniline of 0.25M and 1N of HCl. 0.25 M of ADC was mixed into the reaction mixture with continuous stirring for 5 hours at a room temperature to polymerize into polyaniline. Precipitated product which was left behind, was filtered and unreacted particles can be removed by vacuuming and washing with distilled water and 1N HCl. The product was obtained, dried, and then sample was grinded to get PANI.

2.3. Synthesis of PANI-Dy₂O₃ Composites:

An in-situ chemical polymerization reaction method was employed in the synthesizing of PANI-Dy₂O₃. The formation of aniline hydroxide can be achieved by adding Monomer aniline of 0.25M and 1N of HCl. 0.25 M of ADC was mixed dropwise with the reactant composition. Stoichiometric quantities of Dy₂O₃ were added before the formation of the final product with varying wt% and kept for 5 hours for constant stirring at room temperature. After completion of polymerization, Precipitated product which was left behind, was filtered and unreacted particles can be removed by vacuuming and washing with distilled water and 1N HCl. The product was obtained, dried, and then sample was grinded to get PANI-Dy₂O₃.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

3.1. X-ray diffraction Analysis:

As can be seen in the figure 1. There are X-ray diffraction patterns of polyaniline and polyaniline-Dy₂O₃ composites. A wide peak is evident in the pure PANI at 2θ around the angle 26°, According to this, the PANI is amorphous in nature. The peak could be explained by scattering from the PANI chain while spacing between planes. composite peaks have changed as Dy₂O₃ concentration expands within the composite (8). A new peak occurs at 2θ angles as the Dy₂O₃ oxide quantity increases, similar to their fluctuation in peak intensity, full width at half maximum (FWHM) measurements were used to determine its crystalline size in combination with the following: Debye-Scherrer's formula (9)

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{B \cos \theta}$$

Where B-FWHM of the peak measured in radians

k- constant taken as 0.9

λ- wavelength of the X-rays used (λ = 0.1541 nm)

2θ is the Bragg angle.

42.872 nm, 45.209 nm, 58.98 nm, 60.13 nm, and 63.50 nm represent the crystalline sizes of PANI-Dy₂O₃ composites as 5 to 25% respectively. It is evident from the results that PANI molecules are interconnected to Dy₂O₃ molecules.

Figure 1: X-ray diffraction patterns of Pure PANI and PANI-Dy₂O₃ composites

3.2. Thermal gravimetric Analysis:

Pure PANI and PANI-Dy₂O₃ composite's TGA curve showed a weightloss pattern that consisted of five-step as shown in figure 2. It was claimed that the loss of water absorbed is the reason for the initial weight loss between 29 to 200 °C. The breakdown of dopant causes a second weight loss between 200 and 360 °C (10). The degradation and decomposition of the backbone units of PANI found to be the cause of third weight loss which started at 360 and ended at 420 °C (7), and the fourth weight loss is between 420 to 580 °C. the fifth weight loss in Dy₂O₃-doped PANI from 580 to 790 °C. It can be seen from the TGA thermogram above that the interplay between PANI and rare earth oxide has a significant impact on thermal stability (11).

Figure 2: TGA Cure of Pure PANI, PANI-Dy₂O₃-5% and PANI-Dy₂O₃-25%

3.3. Differential Scanning Calorimeter Analysis:

The DSC of pure PANI and PANI-Dy₂O₃ has been shown in Figure 3. In the figure, pure PANI exhibits an extremely strong endothermic peak is observed at 112.21 °C (12). Polyaniline has the ability to observe the transformation of water into moisture which is associated with this peak (13). After the addition of Dy₂O₃ with different weight percentages, the endothermic peak is at 335.7 and 355.7 °C. The composite's endothermic peak has risen because of the strong intermolecular interaction between PANI and doping materials (14).

Figure 3: DSC Cure of Pure PANI and PANI-Dy₂O₃(5% & 25%)

3.4. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy Analysis:

Figure 4. displays the IR spectrum of polyaniline and PANI-Dy₂O₃ composites, which depicts the transmittance is plotted as a result of wave number (cm⁻¹). To verify functional group's discovery of the interaction between Dy₂O₃ composites and PANI, the FTIR was done. The IR spectra of PANI-Dy₂O₃ composites in the range of 4500–400 cm⁻¹ is depicted in figure 4(15). The band assignments of samples are outlined in Table 1. The quinoid ring plays a significant role in higher characteristic peak between 1506–1591 cm⁻¹, when there is a lower vibration at 1499–1511 cm⁻¹ indicates that there is a of benzenoid ring units present for PANI–Dy₂O₃ composites (16). It is therefore possible to deduce that nanocomposite absorption frequencies are highly affected by the monomer molecules have been suggested as being involved, the nanoparticles and the macromolecular chain of PANI are interrelated. The in-situ polymerization method was

used to adsorption on the surface of Dy₂O₃ composites (17). It has been observed that stretching frequencies in the composites have moved to the higher frequency side, it is possible that the Vanderwall interaction between Dy₂O₃ and the polyaniline chain (18).

Figure 4: FTIR Patterns of Pure PANI and PANI-Dy₂O₃ composites.

3.5. AC Conductivity:

The frequency-dependent variation of AC conductivity for polyaniline and polyaniline-Dy₂O₃ composites is shown in Figure 5. It has been observed that in both PANI and all the cases, σ_{ac} increases after 10² Hz. [19] when it comes to composites that contain 5, 10, and 15 wt% of Dy₂O₃ in PANI, the conductivity increases after 10³ Hz, and in the case of composites with 20 and 25 wt%, the conductivity remains constant after 10³ Hz.

These composites conductivity behavior is anomalous because of the variation in the distribution of Dy₂O₃ in PANI, i.e., the weight percentage of Dy₂O₃ in PANI (20).

Figure 5: AC Conductivity graphs of Pure PANI and PANI- Dy₂O₃ composites of (5% & 25%)

3.6. FESEM Analysis:

The morphology of the Pure PANI and PANI- Dy₂O₃ composites as shown in Figure 6. These morphology images were obtained from FESEM. Figure 6a shows the monotonous distribution of granulated structures of pure PANI [20], and the micrograph of PANI indicates the agglomerated globular structure. Among the five composites that were synthesized using Dy₂O₃ with different weights of 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25, in the image

shown in figure 6b, the micrograph of PANI-Dy₂O₃-25% clearly indicates a highly branched chain structure. The presence of Dy₂O₃ has a significant impact on different electrical parameters, including conductivity (21).

Figure 6: FESEM images of Pure PANI and PANI-Dy₂O₃-25% composite.

CONCLUSIONS:

In polyaniline synthesis, there are a multitude of different methods that can be used to control its structure and physicochemical properties. In-situ chemical polymerization reactions were used for synthesis. The objective of this study was to examine the influence of Dy₂O₃ particles on the electrochemical and attributes of the composites. The composites properties were effectively improved by incorporation of Dy₂O₃. Dy₂O₃ particles had an impact on the structure of PANI in the composite, as demonstrated by the structural and morphological characterization through the interaction between PANI chains and Dy₂O₃ particles can be formed. When amount of Dy₂O₃ increased, the conductivity of the composites increases. hence, the AC conductivity results are strongly influenced by Dy₂O₃ wt%. PANI- Dy₂O₃ composites diverse properties are utilized as a material in sensors, fuel cells, solar batteries, and many other purposes.

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